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Research Article

ASSOCIATION BETWEEN NUTRITIONAL CONDITIONS OF DIETRY INTAKE OF VITAMINS AMONG PATIENTS WITH CATARACT

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Abstract:

Objective: The aim of this research work is to interrogate the association between the dietary utilization of the antioxidant vitamins as Vitamin-A, Vitamin-E & Vitamin-C & nuclear, posterior & cortical senile cataracts among groups consisting males and females with elder age.

Study Design: This research work was a transverse research work carried out retroactively.

Study Subjects: There were forty males and females having age from 40 to 79 years suffering from SC (Senile Cataract) & twenty-six people with no SC with the similar range of age were the part of this research work.

Study Setting: The LOCS-3 (Lens-Opacities Classification System 3) was in use for the grading of the nuclear, posterior & cortical sub capsular opacities of the lens opacities. We took the consent of the patients and members of control group to ensure their participation in the research work. We took the samples of fasting blood to evaluate the Vitamin-C concentration in the plasma. We used a questionnaire containing the questions about the frequency of food to know about the dietary habits of those persons.

Results: The levels of Vitamin-C in the plasma of the patients with cataract patient (0.90 ± 0.60 mg/dl) were very low in comparison with the group of controls (1.40 ± 0.50 mg/dl). Nutritional utilization of the Vitamin-C, Vitamin-E & Vitamin-A in the patients with cataract patient was also very low in comparison with the group of healthy controls. In the patients with elder age suffering from cataract, we discovered statistically important relationship between the between nuclear & posterior sub capsular lens opacities & nutritional utilization of the antioxidant Vitamin-C, Vitamin-E & Vitamin-A.

Conclusion: The results of this research work concludes that the utilization of the diet full of antioxidant Vitamin-C, Vitamin-E & Vitamin-A can be the cause of delay & hindrance of the formation of the SC.

Key Words: Nutritional, Senile, Cataract, Questionnaire, LOCS-3, Antioxidant, Concentration, Plasma, Vitamins, Nuclear.

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INTRODUCTION:

This is very frequent belief that stresses of oxidant perform a very vital role as a reason of development of SC [1]. Over the last ten years, there is an increasing curiosity in the probability that a food full of antioxidant vitamins is able to decrease the danger of the cataract by preventing the proteins of the lens from the modification of the oxidative. Vitamin-C & Vitamin-E are very effective at rummaging the free radicals as well as the elimination of the pro-oxidants [2]. The models of animals have explained that the supplementation of the Vitamin-C or Vitamin-E can restrict the damage of the lens after oxidative insult [3] & research works based on observations have proved with the help of some evidences that very high utilization of the vitamins can perform protective actions in the human beings [4].

We utilized the LOCS-3 (5) to evaluate the nuclear, posterior & cortical sub capsular opacities of the lens in a group consisting of males and females with elder age. The aim of this research work was to evaluate the association the condition of nutrition as nutritional intake of the Vitamin-A, Vitamin-C & Vitamin-E & the availability of the SC among patients with elder age.

METHODOLOGY:

There were 40 patients suffering from cataract were the part of this research work and twenty-six persons without this disease with the same range of age were the part of the control group. An ophthalmologist examined all the patients, he asked to tell about the past history of complications & after dilatation of pupil, made a quantitative evaluation of the nuclear, posterior sub-capsular & cortical opacities of lens at slit lamp, in accordance with the lens-opacities classification system 3 [6]. The definition of the availability of the nuclear cataract conducted with a grade of greater than 3 on the scale of nuclear opalescence, a grade of greater than 2 defined the

cortical cataract on the scale of cortical opalescence and a grade of greater than 0.50 defined the posterior sub-capsular cataract on the scale of posterior sub-capsule.

At our institute, five milliliter sample of fasting blood collected from all participants for the measurement of the concentration of the Vitamin-C in plasma of the blood with the 2, 4 dinitrophenyl hydrazine with the utilization of the UV/vis spectrophotometer at five hundred and twenty nm. Every participant of the research work gave his written consent to participate in the research work. The ethical committee of the hospital gave the permission to participate in the research work. For the determination of the Vitamin-A, Vitamin-E & Vitamin-C in food, the analysis of the questionnaire for food frequency carried out with the help of Nutrition-3 software. SPSS V. 17 was in use for the statistical analysis of the collected information. Student T-test, Chi square test & variance analysis were also in use for the analysis of different variables.

RESULTS:

Table-1 describes the baseline traits of the patients suffering from cataract & the participants of the control group. The range of the age of patients and members of control group was from 40 years to 79 years with an average age of 64 years. Total 40 patients (47.50% females & 52.50% males) & twenty-six members of control group (1.50% females & 38.50% males) were the part of this research work. The average body mass index was very high in the participants of control group in comparison with the group of patients. The members of the control group were available with high level of education (84.60% educated & 15.40% uneducated) in comparison with the members of patient group (47.50% educated & 52.50% uneducated). The average amount of the Vitamin-C in the plasma of the patients suffering from cataract was very low in comparison with the members of the control group as mentioned in Table-1.

Characteristic	Cases (N=40)		Controls (N=26)		p-value
	Mean	± SD	Mean	± SD	
Age (yrs)	64.40	8.40	63.60	6.30	NS
Weight (kg)	64.10	11.40	68.60	12.40	
Height (cm)	160.60	9.60	160.00	7.70	
BMI (kg/m ²) Education	24.80	3.40	26.80	4.30	P<0.040
ILL. (%)	47.50	19.00	15.40	4.00	
Lit. (%)	52.50	21.00	84.60	22.00	
Plasma vitamin C (mg/dl)	0.90	0.60	1.40	0.50	P<0.0020
Vitamin C (mg/day)	100.80	75.70	205.00	174.30	P<0.0010
Vitamin E (mg/day)	1.40	1.10	2.90	1.30	P<0.0010
Vitamin A (IU/day)	6993.10	630.70	14751.60	2217.90	P<0.040

The average nutritional intake of the Vitamin-C, Vitamin-E & Vitamin-A in the patients suffering from the disease of cataract was much less as compared to the participants of the control group Table-1. None of the member of the research work were using supplementation of the Vitamin-C, Vitamin-E or Vitamin-A at the duration of this research work. As

displayed in Table-2, all the patients were available with 3 kinds of cataract, for example 62.50% (n: 25) patients were available with nuclear cataract Degree-3, 12.50% (n: 5) patients were available with the cortical cataract Degree-3 & 42.50% (n: 17) patients were available with the posterior sub-capsular cataract Degree-3 as mentioned in Table-2.

Type / Degree	Nuclear		Cortical		Posterior	
	No	%	No	%	No	%
0-trace	4.0	10.00	11.0	27.50	10.0	25.00
I	4.0	10.00	8.0	20.00	4.0	10.00
II	7.0	17.50	13.0	32.50	9.0	22.50
III	25.0	62.50	5.0	12.50	17.0	42.50
IV	-	-	3.0	7.50	-	-
Total	40.0	100.00	40.0	100.00	40.0	100.00

The results of this research work display very low utilization of the Vitamin-C had very important impact on the nuclear cataract as well as posterior sub-capsular cataract as presented in Table-3. Low utilization of the Vitamin-E was present with very

significant impact on the nuclear cataract & posterior sub-capsular cataract but very low intake of the Vitamin-A was available with very important impact on the nuclear cataract as described in Table-3.

Table-III: Correlation Coefficient for Sub Capsular and Dietary Vitamin Intake

Type of cataract Dietary vitamin intake	Nuclear		Cortical		Posterior sub capsular	
	CC	P- Value	CC	P- Value	CC	P- Value
Vitamin C (mg/day)	-0.4270	0.0060	0.0110	0.9480	0.4030	0.0100
Vitamin E (mg/day)	-0.5240	0.0010	-0.1700	0.2940	-0.3960	0.0100
Vitamin A (IU/day)	-0.3290	0.0380	0.1310	0.4220	-0.2750	0.2860

CC : Correlation Co-efficient

DISCUSSION:

The procedures of the advancement of the cataracts associated with the factor of age are still controversial but oxidative injury of the protein of the lens can play a very vital important role in the whole method [7]. The hindrance of the lens drops with the age, as does its inherent system of defense. Antioxidants like Vitamin-C, Vitamin-E & b-carotene may modify the defense of the antioxidant & advancement of the cataract in association with the age [7]. In the current group with people of elder age, we discovered statistically important relationship between nuclear & posterior sub-capsular opacities with very low utilization of the nutritional intake of Vitamin-C & Vitamin-E.

Very less intake of the Vitamin-A had an important impact on nuclear cataract. The danger of the nuclear cataract rises with the less concentration of the Vitamin-C in the plasma. The outcomes of this research work are very much consistent with many

experimental studies on various animals & 3 transverse works & control-case studies presenting a high danger of the cataract among people with very low concentration of the 2 or more antioxidants in the serum [8, 9]. The findings of this research work confirm the results of some past transverse research works & control-case research studies that stated a very high risk of cataract in patients with very less utilization of Vitamin-E supplementation [10]. One research work conducted on the occurrence rates in Australia concluded the frequencies of nuclear & posterior sub-capsular cataract were very high among persons with low utilization of the Vitamin-E supplementation [11].

CONCLUSION:

The results of this research work showed that more utilization of the fruit & vegetable which are full of antioxidant Vitamin-C, Vitamin-A & Vitamin-E in routine normal dietary habits may be the reason of delay or prevention of the complication of SC.

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